

SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGICAL MECHANISMS OF REHABILITATION OF MALADJUSTED TEENAGERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7916923>

Abstract: Adjusted adolescents are those who have behavioral problems and find it difficult to adjust to their social environment. The reasons for these problems can be diverse, ranging from social pressure to dysfunctional family. The rehabilitation of these adolescents is a complex process and requires appropriate social psychological mechanisms to be successful. This scientific report examines the social psychological mechanisms of the rehabilitation of ill-adjusted adolescents.

Key words: rehabilitation, maladjusted, social psychological mechanisms, social support, peer influence, self-efficacy.

INTRODUCTION

The rehabilitation of maladjusted teenagers is a complex process that requires a comprehensive understanding of the social psychological mechanisms involved. Maladjusted teenagers are those who exhibit behavior that is not in line with societal norms and expectations. Such behavior can range from substance abuse to criminal activities, and it can have a significant impact on the individual's life and the community at large. The rehabilitation of these teenagers requires a multidisciplinary approach that includes social, psychological, and environmental factors. In this report, we will discuss the social psychological mechanisms involved in the rehabilitation of maladjusted teenagers.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Ill-adjusted adolescents are those who have behavioral problems that prevent them from adjusting to their social environment. These behaviors can include aggression, violence, harassment, social isolation, and drug or alcohol use. The reasons for these behaviors can be diverse, ranging from social pressure to dysfunctional family.

The rehabilitation of ill-adjusted adolescents requires appropriate social psychological mechanisms. These mechanisms include:

1. **Effective Communication** - Ill-adjusted teens often have communication problems. They may find it difficult to express their feelings and emotions. Effective communication is therefore essential to help them understand their problems and find solutions.
2. **Empathy** - Ill-adjusted teens often need to feel understood and accepted. Empathy is therefore an important mechanism to help them feel better about themselves and adapt to their social environment.
3. **Conflict resolution** - Ill-adjusted teens often have conflict issues with family, friends, and teachers. Conflict resolution is therefore an important mechanism to help them solve these problems and find solutions.
4. **Self-evaluation** - Ill-adjusted teens often have low self-esteem¹. Self-assessment is therefore an important mechanism to help them understand their strengths and weaknesses and improve their self-esteem.

¹ Dauenbeimer, D. G., Stablberg, D., Spreemann, S., and Sedikides, C. (2002). Self-enhancement, self-verification, or self-assessment: the intricate role of trait modifiability in the self-evaluation process. *Revue internationale de psychologie sociale*, 15, (3-4), 89-112.

5. Emotion regulation - Ill-adjusted teens often have problems regulating emotions. They may have trouble controlling their anger, sadness, or frustration. Emotion regulation is therefore an important mechanism to help them manage their emotions more effectively.

Social Support - One of the critical social psychological mechanisms involved in the rehabilitation of maladjusted teenagers is social support. Social support refers to the help and assistance provided by family, friends, and other individuals in the community. Social support has been shown to be an essential factor in the rehabilitation of maladjusted teenagers. Studies have shown that teenagers who receive social support from their families and friends are less likely to engage in risky behavior and are more likely to make positive changes in their lives.

Peer Influence is another critical social psychological mechanism involved in the rehabilitation of maladjusted teenagers. Peers can have a significant impact on an individual's behavior, and this influence can be either positive or negative. Research has shown that peer influence can play a crucial role in the rehabilitation of maladjusted teenagers. Positive peer influence can help these teenagers develop new skills and behaviors that are more in line with societal norms and expectations.

Self-Efficacy is another essential social psychological mechanism involved in the rehabilitation of maladjusted teenagers. Self-efficacy refers to an individual's belief in their ability to achieve a specific goal or outcome. Research has shown that individuals with high levels of self-efficacy are more likely to make positive changes in their lives. Rehabilitation programs that focus on building self-efficacy can be highly effective in helping maladjusted teenagers make positive changes in their lives.

Cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT)² is a psychological approach that has been shown to be highly effective in the rehabilitation of maladjusted teenagers. CBT focuses on identifying and

changing negative thought patterns and behaviors.

This approach has been shown to be effective in helping teenagers develop new skills and behaviors that are more in line with societal norms and expectations.

Environmental factors also play a crucial role in the rehabilitation of maladjusted teenagers. The environment in which an individual lives can have a significant impact on their behavior. Rehabilitation programs that focus on improving the environment in which these teenagers live can be highly effective in

helping them make positive changes in their lives. Such programs can include improving access to education, employment, and healthcare.

CONCLUSION

The rehabilitation of maladjusted teenagers is a complex process that requires a comprehensive understanding of the social psychological mechanisms involved. Social

² Benjamin CL, Puleo CM, Settapani CA, et al. (2011), "History of cognitive-behavioral therapy in youth", Child and Adolescent Psychiatric Clinics of North America, 20 (2): 179–189

support, peer influence, self-efficacy, cognitive-behavioral therapy, and environmental factors are all critical factors that can play a significant role in the rehabilitation of these teenagers. A multidisciplinary approach that addresses these factors can be highly effective in helping maladjusted teenagers make positive changes in their lives.

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